

Review:

“Industrie 4.0” and Smart Manufacturing – A Review of Research Issues and Application Examples

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1 A fourth industrial revolution is propagated in
 2 global manufacturing. It is based on the
 3 introduction of Internet of Things and Servitization
 4 concepts into manufacturing companies, leading to
 5 vertically and horizontally integrated production
 6 systems. The resulting Smart Factories are able to
 7 fulfill dynamic customer demands with high
 8 variability in small lot sizes while integrating
 9 human ingenuity and automation. To support the
 10 manufacturing industry in this conversion process
 11 and enhance global competitiveness, policy makers
 12 in several countries have established research and
 13 technology transfer schemes. Most prominently,
 14 Germany has enacted its ‘Industrie 4.0’ program,
 15 which is increasingly affecting European policy,
 16 while the United States focus on Smart
 17 Manufacturing. Other industrial nations have
 18 established their own programs on Smart
 19 Manufacturing, notably Japan and Korea. This
 20 shows that manufacturing intelligence has become
 21 a crucial topic for research and industry worldwide.
 22 The main object of these activities are so-called
 23 Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS): physical entities
 24 (e.g. machines, vehicles, work pieces etc.), which are
 25 equipped with technologies such as RFID, sensors,
 26 microprocessors, telematics or complete embedded
 27 systems. They are characterized by being able to
 28 collect data of themselves and their environment,
 29 process and evaluate this data, connect and
 30 communicate with other systems and initiate
 31 actions. In addition, CPS enable new services that
 32 can replace traditional business models based solely
 33 on product sales. The objective of this paper is to
 34 give an overview of Industrie 4.0 and Smart
 35 Manufacturing programs, analyze the application
 36 potential of CPS, starting from product design,
 37 through production and logistics, up to
 38 maintenance and exploitation (e.g. recycling) and
 39 identify current and future research issues. Besides
 40 the technical perspective, the paper also takes into
 41 account the economic side with the new business
 42 strategies and models made possible.

43 **Keywords:** Industry 4.0, Smart Manufacturing,
 44 Cyber-Physical Systems, Industrial Internet, Smart
 45 Factory

46 1. Introduction

47 Three industrial revolutions have led to paradigm
 48 changes in the domain of manufacturing so far:
 49 mechanization through water and steam power, mass
 50 production in assembly lines, and automation using
 51 information technology. However, over the past years,
 52 industry, together with researchers and policy makers
 53 worldwide have increasingly advocated an upcoming
 54 fourth industrial revolution (see Fig. 1.).

55
56 **Fig. 1.** Four Industrial Revolutions

57 For example, the German government promotes the
 58 computerization of manufacturing industries in their
 59 ‘Industrie 4.0’ (I4.0) program [1,2], while in the United
 60 States Smart Manufacturing initiatives, like, e.g., the
 61 Smart Manufacturing Leadership Coalition (SMLC),
 62 drives and facilitates the broad adoption of
 63 manufacturing intelligence [3]. Other major
 64 manufacturing countries, like Japan [4] and Korea [5]
 65 have also established national programs on Smart
 66 Manufacturing.

67 The fourth industrial revolution is characterized by
 68 the introduction of the *Internet of Things* (IoT) and
 69 *Internet of Services* concepts into manufacturing,
 70 which enables *Smart Factories* with vertically and
 71 horizontally integrated production systems. In this
 72 world, highly flexible processes that can be changed
 73 on-the-fly enable individualized mass production.
 74 Variants are self-determined through items delivering
 75 their own production data to intelligent machines [6],
 76 which are aware of the environment, exchange
 77 information and control processes in production and

1 logistics themselves. Data is collected along the whole
 2 life-cycle in large quantities and stored decentralized
 3 to enable local decisions, but still transparent to be
 4 exchanged with partners. In order to realize this vision,
 5 elements like machines, storage systems and utilities
 6 need to be able to share information, as well as act and
 7 control each other autonomously. Such systems are
 8 called *Cyber-Physical Systems* (CPS) [7].

9 CPS emerge through the complex networking and
 10 integration of embedded systems, application systems,
 11 and infrastructure, enabled by human machine
 12 interaction. In contrast to conventional systems used
 13 for production or logistics, CPS can be seen as *systems*
 14 *of systems*, which require the collaboration of different
 15 disciplines such as mechanical engineering, electrical
 16 engineering, and computer science for their
 17 realization [8].

18 The industrial transformation associated with the
 19 Smart Manufacturing revolution and the introduction
 20 of CPS creates numerous challenges for organizations,
 21 technology and employees. All in all, as illustrated in
 22 Fig. 1., complexity in production has increased with
 23 each industrial revolution. Dynamic socio-technical
 24 systems have emerged, that consist of a great number
 25 of tangible, intangible and also human elements. This
 26 complexity has to be managed by appropriate methods
 27 and tools. Furthermore, the interaction between
 28 humans and machines requires the right interfaces and
 29 concepts to be efficient and safe. New and innovative
 30 services are possible based on CPS technology, but
 31 they also need new innovative business models to be
 32 profitable [9].

33 I4.0, Smart Manufacturing and the other initiatives
 34 aim to provide the foundation to overcome these
 35 challenges and support manufacturing companies and
 36 their stakeholders in their transition to Smart
 37 Manufacturing. They aim to develop and deliver
 38 appropriate models, methods and tools for
 39 manufacturing companies, as well as establishing
 40 prototype implementations that can be used as
 41 exemplary blueprints for other companies that are
 42 interested in this development.

43 The objective of this paper is to give an overview
 44 about these initiatives, with a focus on I4.0 and Smart
 45 Manufacturing, and provide selected application
 46 examples. Based on the results, current and future
 47 research issues for Smart Manufacturing will be
 48 identified. The next chapter (2) introduces the scope
 49 and methodology of the review, while chapter 3
 50 describes the different initiatives. Chapter 4 illustrates
 51 application scenarios and research issues and the paper
 52 is concluded in chapter 5.

53 2. Scope and Methodology

54 The scope of this review comprises an overview on
 55 current smart manufacturing initiatives, research
 56 issues and application examples. This includes trends
 57 in manufacturing to utilize the Internet of Things and
 58 related services, as well as the resulting industrial

59 practices. In this paper, Smart Manufacturing refers
 60 mainly to the use of intelligent machines, so called
 61 Cyber-Physical Systems that are networked, context-
 62 aware and self-controlled. The focus of the review lies
 63 on the European, specifically German, Industrie 4.0
 64 initiative and Smart Manufacturing activities in the
 65 United States. Other programs, e.g. in Japan and Korea
 66 (Smart Factory) are recognized, but not analyzed in
 67 detail.

68 The methodology of the review is based on two
 69 pillars, a literature review on the state-of-the-art in
 70 Smart Manufacturing and I4.0, as well as studying
 71 application scenarios from research and industry. For
 72 the literature review, fundamental official publications
 73 from the initiatives have been taken into account.
 74 Additionally, relevant papers identified through title,
 75 abstract and keywords from interdisciplinary search
 76 engines such as SCOPUS have been analyzed.
 77 Regarding the application scenarios, light-house
 78 projects from research and industry, in some of which
 79 the authors are directly involved, have been studied in
 80 order to identify current and future research issues.

81 3. Definitions and Frameworks

82 This section introduces definitions and frameworks
 83 in the scope of Smart Manufacturing. First, the main
 84 initiatives of Industrie 4.0 in Germany and Smart
 85 Manufacturing in the United States are presented.
 86 Following, other initiatives and related terms are
 87 described.

88 3.1. Industrie 4.0

89 For Germany, having one of the most competitive
 90 manufacturing industries in the world and a strong
 91 machinery and plant fabrication, it is vital to master the
 92 challenges of a fourth industrial revolution. Therefore,
 93 the German government has established its Industrie
 94 4.0 program [1] to keep Germany a manufacturing
 95 country. It is based on the assumption that “*industrial*
 96 *production in the near future will be characterized by*
 97 *the strong individualization of products under the*
 98 *conditions of highly flexible (large series) production,*
 99 *the extensive integration of customers and business*
 100 *partners in business and value-added processes, and*
 101 *the linking of production and high-quality services that*
 102 *leads to so-called hybrid products” [11].*

103 I4.0 comprises a paradigm shift from automated
 104 manufacturing towards an intelligent manufacturing
 105 concept. Physical and virtual world grow together and
 106 objects (incl. machines) are equipped with sensors and
 107 actuators [10]. The intelligent manufacturing
 108 implementation will make use of concepts like the
 109 Internet of Things to facilitate this change. The
 110 exclusive feature in I4.0 is to fulfill the individual
 111 customer requirements with product variants in a very
 112 small lot size, down to one-off items [2]. Availability
 113 of all relevant information in real-time will enable the
 114 manufacturing system to meet customer requirements
 115 without waste for re-configuration of assembly line or

1 set-up times through dynamic business and
 2 engineering processes (see Fig. 2.).

3 Source: Final report of the working group Industrie 4.0 [1]

4 **Fig. 2.** CPS Vision for Industrie 4.0

5
 6 In this context, the Smart Manufacturing and
 7 logistics systems can not only generate the optimal
 8 value stream to fulfil the real-time demands, but also
 9 create new business models based on better predictive
 10 maintenance, robustness in product design and
 11 adaptive logistics.

12 Industrie 4.0 addresses research and development
 13 actions in eight key areas to support the adoption of its
 14 principles in industry [1]:

- 15 i. *Standardization and reference architecture:*
 16 Collaborative partnerships of organizations in
 17 value networks requires a set of common
 18 standards in a reference architecture.
- 19 ii. *Managing complex systems:* The higher
 20 complexity of systems and products require
 21 appropriate models for their management.
- 22 iii. *A comprehensive broadband infrastructure
 23 for industry:* The Internet of Things requires
 24 a reliable and fast communication network
 25 infrastructure.
- 26 iv. *Safety and security:* Related to close human-
 27 machine interaction, manufacturing systems
 28 must not harm people or the environment.
 29 Furthermore, data and information need
 30 access authorization and privacy measures.
- 31 v. *Work organisation and design:* Along with
 32 the machines, also the environment and
 33 processes of work will change, giving the
 34 employee greater freedom and responsibility.
- 35 vi. *Training and continuing professional
 36 development:* In relation to the previous key
 37 area, the worker needs to qualified through
 38 suitable training and life-long learning.
- 39 vii. *Regulatory framework:* Together with the
 40 organizational changes, also legislation has to
 41 take new innovation into account, especially
 42 for privacy and liability regulations.
- 43 viii. *Resource efficiency:* By improving
 44 productivity and resource efficiency,

45 consumption of raw material and energy
 46 should be lowered.

47 Along with the actions in the key areas,
 48 manufacturing companies have to develop new
 49 business strategies for I4.0. Value networks and
 50 profit/loss sharing will be strongly linked to the
 51 individual customer problem. Responsibilities and
 52 privacy rules are described in Service Level
 53 Agreements (SLA) [1].

54 In Germany, the federal government has been
 55 funding the research agenda Industrie 4.0 through
 56 several programs during the last years. While the
 57 Federal Ministry of Education and Research has
 58 published seven calls with an overall funding of
 59 € 120 million, the Federal Ministry for Economic
 60 Affairs and Energy has funded projects with another
 61 € 80 million [12].

62 3.2. Smart Manufacturing

63 Smart Manufacturing is a term coined by several
 64 agencies like the Department of Energy (DoE) and the
 65 National Institute of Standards and Technology
 66 (NIST) in the United States. Wallace and Riddick [13]
 67 describe Smart Manufacturing in short as “a data
 68 intensive application of information technology at the
 69 shop floor level and above to enable intelligent,
 70 efficient and responsive operations”. While there are
 71 multiple more comprehensive definitions available
 72 (e.g. [14]), they all highlight the use of Information and
 73 Communication Technology (ICT) and advanced data
 74 analytics to improve manufacturing operations at all
 75 levels of the supply network, be it the shop floor [15],
 76 factory [16] or Supply Chain [14,17]. Some authors go
 77 even a step further and extend the Smart
 78 Manufacturing framework beyond manufacturing
 79 itself, highlighting the lifecycle perspective [18]. This
 80 broad focus already highlights the close proximity to
 81 other established areas like Industrie 4.0 (see previous
 82 section) and Intelligent Manufacturing (Systems) [19].

83 Smart Manufacturing incorporates various
 84 technologies, including but not limited to CP(P)S, IoT,
 85 robotics/automation, big data analytics and cloud
 86 computing [20,21] to realize the vision of a data-driven,
 87 connected supply network. An important aspect that
 88 differentiates Smart Manufacturing from many other
 89 initiatives, is the specific emphasis on human
 90 ingenuity within the framework. Humans are not to be
 91 simply replaced by Artificial Intelligence and
 92 automation on the shop floor but their capabilities are
 93 to be enhanced by smartly designing the customized
 94 solution for the specific area. The importance of
 95 product and process information and data, enabling
 96 technology and (human or machine inherent)
 97 knowledge is commonly accepted. Highlighting the
 98 broad and comprehensive scope of Smart
 99 Manufacturing, its three main pillars are [14]:

- 100 • Plantwide optimization
- 101 • Sustainable production
- 102 • Agile supply chains

1 In the United States, several federal funding
2 agencies have calls for funding placed to drive Smart
3 Manufacturing. For example, the DoE has announced
4 up to US\$ 70 million in funding in Smart
5 Manufacturing [22], NIST had several calls for their
6 Smart Manufacturing program with a budget of ca.
7 US\$ 30 million per year. Several other initiatives offer
8 additional opportunities in this area or closely related
9 ones, like the Smart Manufacturing Leadership
10 Coalition (SMCLC) or NSF’s Cybermanufacturing
11 program.

12 3.3. Other related terms and initiatives

13 *Intelligent Manufacturing / Intelligent*
14 *Manufacturing Systems (IMS)*: Intelligent
15 Manufacturing is sometimes used synonymously to
16 Smart Manufacturing. While the close collaboration of
17 the IMS organization with the several Smart
18 Manufacturing funding agencies and research
19 institutions support this, there is a notion that
20 Intelligent Manufacturing may focus more on the
21 technical aspects and less on the organizational ones.
22 Kumar’s [19] definition of an intelligent
23 manufacturing process as having “the ability to self-
24 regulate and/or self-control to manufacture the product
25 within the design specifications” shows that at least
26 some researchers see Intelligent Manufacturing more
27 focused on the analytics and control aspects. However,
28 the original definition from the later 1980ies by
29 Yoshikawa [23] emphasize the importance of humans
30 within the system as well, supporting the similarity to
31 Smart Manufacturing.

32 *Smart Factory*: Smart Factory is a term used in
33 different contexts for some time. Some might argue
34 that Smart Factory is focusing more on the individual
35 entity (plant level) [24–26] rather than the broader
36 supply network scope of Smart Manufacturing and
37 Industrie 4.0. In this case the Smart Factory paradigm
38 relates strongly to IIoT and CPS [27]. However, other
39 sources refer specifically to the Industrie 4.0 initiative
40 as the basis for the Smart Factory movement [5,28],
41 with the Korean Smart Factory initiative being at the
42 forefront. Furthermore, the National Science
43 Foundation (USA) has issued a joint call for proposals
44 with the Korean National Research Foundation (NRF)
45 specifically aiming at collaborations including the
46 Smart Manufacturing domain, which indicates that the
47 broader perspective is shared by Smart Factory and
48 that the program’s scope is similar to Smart
49 Manufacturing and Industrie 4.0.

50 *Internet of Things (IoT) / Industrial Internet of*
51 *Things (IIoT)*: Intelligent Manufacturing and Smart
52 Factory paradigms may be argued to be similar to
53 Smart Manufacturing and Industrie 4.0, the Internet of
54 Things (IoT) paradigm is more ICT oriented [29].
55 IoT’s vision of ubiquitous computing [30] is to
56 ‘connect’ the physical world with the virtual world and
57 facilitate communication between all connected
58 entities [31,32]. IoT requires its physical entities to
59 have certain amount of ‘smarts’ incorporated, in the
60 sense of communication, data processing and/or
61 sensing capability. In recent years, a sub-paradigm, the
62 Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) emerged, focusing
63 on the interconnectivity of industrial assets, like
64 manufacturing machines, tools and logistics
65 operations [33]. In this understanding, many of the
66 basic requirements are similar to the ones faced by
67 Smart Manufacturing and Industrie 4.0, e.g., the
68 challenge of interoperability and privacy/security
69 issues [34]. Overall, IoT/IIoT can be understood as an
70 enabling technology similar to CP(P)S [20,35].
71 *Industrial Internet*: The industrial Internet is
72 understood as the unity of (industrial) machines and
73 software [36]. Their global outlet is the Industrial
74 Internet Consortium (IIC) (www.iiconsortium.org).
75 This basic understanding highlights the similarity
76 towards CP(P)S and Industrial Internet of Things
77 (IIoT) [37] as a more technology focused framework.
78 Some argue that the main difference between the
79 Industrial Internet and Smart Manufacturing and
80 Industrie 4.0 is the more focused scope, mainly looking
81 at the machine and maybe shop-floor level instead of
82 the overall supply network [38]. Others understand the
83 Industrial Internet as the foundation for system wide
84 optimization [36].

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82 the overall supply network [38]. Others understand the
83 Industrial Internet as the foundation for system wide
84 optimization [36].

85 4. Applications and Research Issues

86 In this section, two main topics are discussed. Firstly,
87 selected application scenarios and use cases of Smart
88 Manufacturing are presented. Derived from the
89 selected application scenarios and enhanced by
90 literature and experience of the authors, current and
91 future research issues in the context of Smart
92 Manufacturing and I4.0 are discussed thereafter.

93 4.1. Application Scenarios & Use Cases

94 The selection of application scenarios was made to
95 present a broad variety in order to highlight the wide
96 scope of the initiatives. The application cases range
97 from technical initiatives implementing CPS in SME
98 intralogistics [39], over human robot interaction at the
99 shop-floor level using sensors and image recognition
100 [40], to new business models around product
101 enhancing services based on lifecycle and sensor
102 data [41].

103 4.1.1. Cyber-Physical Logistics System

104 The case company in this application scenario is a
105 gear manufacturer from one of the first I4.0 lighthouse
106 projects in Germany that has organized its processes
107 according to the principles of lean production. Stocks
108 in production are kept at a low level despite a high
109 number of variants and intralogistics are managed by a
110 container-Kanban-procedure in combination with a
111 milk run. For every machine, there is a delivery space
112 where only one floor roller (transport unit for several
113 load carriers) for exactly one production order can be
114 placed, and also one pick up area. A human operated
115 electric train services the machines every hour to pick

1 up finished orders and deliver supplies. The machines
 2 are arranged in such a way that the train can reach all
 3 machines by driving an “eight” course. At the
 4 intersection of the loops, it is also possible to turn to
 5 the area for incoming and outgoing goods. Each full
 6 hour all stations are service, picking off finished orders,
 7 distributing them and noting which delivery areas are
 8 empty. These free delivery spaces are equipped with
 9 orders from the buffer stock in the following cycle. The
 10 fixed cycle time leads to a high fluctuation in floor
 11 roller usage and waste of electric train capacity. The
 12 complete loops are always serviced, although there
 13 might be no need for transport, as there is no up-to-date
 14 information about collection and delivery orders.

15 A cyber-physical production system has been
 16 established, featuring a cyber-physical logistic
 17 system (CPLS), to increase the efficiency of lean
 18 production in this scenario, with many variations of
 19 products and not completely levelled and synchronized
 20 production lines. The aim of the CPLS is to increase
 21 the flexibility through autonomous decisions and
 22 enable a reduction of inventories due to the
 23 autonomous solving of errors in real time. The
 24 demand-driven milk run is based on information about
 25 the occupancy of the delivery and pick up spaces.
 26 Furthermore, cyber-physical load carriers (CP-LC)
 27 with sensors to locate themselves and to monitor the
 28 environmental conditions (e.g. temperature,
 29 acceleration) which are affecting the components have
 30 been introduced (see Fig. 3.).

31
 32 **Fig. 3.** Scenario of the Cyber-Physical Production System
 33 (following Reinhart et al. [42])

34 The CP-LCs can communicate with other cyber-
 35 physical systems and can transmit their position to the
 36 intralogistics employee. In this way he gets the
 37 information where delivery or collection needs are
 38 before starting a new cycle. For this purpose, a
 39 tablet PC is chosen on which the current needs are
 40 displayed. On this device, the remaining processing
 41 times of the machines and logs of operational data are
 42 considered to estimate the completion dates of the
 43 current production orders and thereby calculating the
 44 optimal departure time. The employee can now decide
 45 based on this information when he starts the next tour.
 46 Under the restrictions that the machine must not run
 47 “empty” and that only one order can be placed on the

48 delivery space of the machine, the number of cycles
 49 and loops is lowered through networking the
 50 individual logistics units, reducing transport and
 51 motion processes to a minimum. The reduction of
 52 cycles of the milk run has measurable advantages for
 53 the productivity of the case company, because they
 54 have more time for their core activities in
 55 commissioning, shipping and storage. According to a
 56 simulation based on the current capacity of the electric
 57 train, the number of cycles can be reduced by approx.
 58 68 %, while the number of driven loops in the cycles
 59 can be reduced by about 27 %.

60 **4.1.2. Safe Human-Robot Interaction**

61 Smart Manufacturing is different from the pure
 62 automation focus of previous initiatives. For a smart
 63 robotics’ factory within the context of I4.0 and IoT,
 64 where high productivity is demanded by the market,
 65 collaboration between human workers and robots is the
 66 key. Human workers are essential in their role of either
 67 supervisor, collaborator and for jobs robots are not
 68 trained or capable of. These so called co-bots
 69 (collaborative robots) [43] are a dedicated area of
 70 research and several companies already brought forth
 71 their vision of such systems.

72 The constant human presence in or near the robot’s
 73 work area forces companies to rethink how a robotic
 74 work space is organized and shared with its human
 75 counterparts. Traditionally, the robotic work area was
 76 fenced of and prohibited for the humans to enter during
 77 operation due to safety concerns (see Fig. 4.).

78
 79 **Fig. 4.** Traditional protection solution

80 Within the I4.0 initiative, the presented application
 81 research focuses on new ways to a) ensure the safety
 82 of human workers and b) limit the restrictions of a
 83 divided workspace. The core of this robotic factory
 84 CPS development is the integration of dynamic
 85 characteristics of the individual components. The
 86 individual protection components register context,
 87 situation and status of worker, machine, plant and
 88 process and activate protective mechanisms before a
 89 hazard, e.g. collision, can occur. The production
 90 process will run without threats and interruptions and
 91 this will achieve the level of security and safety,
 92 meeting worker safety legal requirements on the shop
 93 floor. Symbiotic human–robot collaboration [37] is

1 defined for a fenceless environment in which
 2 productivity and resource effectiveness can be
 3 improved by combining the flexibility of humans and
 4 the accuracy of machines. Robotic CPS can enable
 5 such human–robot collaboration with the
 6 characteristics of dynamic task planning, active
 7 collision avoidance, and adaptive robot control.
 8 Humans are part of the CPS design, in which human
 9 instructions to robots by speech, signs or hand gestures
 10 are possible during collaborative handling, assembly,
 11 packaging, food processing or other tasks. All of these
 12 industrial tasks bring the focus of current research to
 13 human robot collaboration on heavy payload robots.
 14 The approach is to exhibit safe intermediate Human-
 15 Robot Collaboration (HRC) without any fencing. In
 16 order to realize this, extra safety and protection
 17 measures need to be implemented for a collaborative
 18 robotic cyber physical system (CPS) (see Fig. 5.).

Fig. 5. CPS protection solution

19
 20
 21 The human component is well connected through
 22 different adaptor technologies, e.g. human position
 23 tracking, and safety distance parameters are important
 24 considerations for worker safety in the robotic CPS.
 25 The robotic CPS is a highly automated system as it
 26 removes the boundaries between the composite
 27 elements and supporting their operational interactions;
 28 thus achieving a truly smart system with humans in the
 29 loop, enabled by connected entities that are able to
 30 sense, interpret and react.

31 **4.1.3. Video Surveillance as a Service**

32 This application scenario describes a use case from
 33 an ongoing European research project on Servitization
 34 of manufacturing. The case company is a vendor for
 35 the aviation sector, which offers fully integrated
 36 solutions for surveillance systems. This Aircraft
 37 Security Video System (ASVS) is an integrated, video-
 38 based infrastructure. As a modular solution, the system
 39 consolidates several components, all of which are
 40 required by a universal surveillance system for
 41 aviation. The focus of the use case is on the Cabin
 42 Video Surveillance System (CVSS), which helps flight
 43 attendants to monitor the cabin area while the aircraft
 44 is in flight. It generates video streams, which are stored
 45 on a memory cartridge within the Central Video
 46 Unit (CVU/DVR). These systems are customized,

47 individual turnkey solutions, certified according to
 48 aviation standards and approved by aviation
 49 authorities. Customers are airlines, which retrofit their
 50 aircraft with the buyer furnished surveillance solutions
 51 from the vendor. In general, the design, manufacturing,
 52 operation and maintenance of aircraft and (airborne)
 53 aircraft equipment are strictly regulated by authorities
 54 (mainly EASA, FAA and local authorities), which
 55 means that in the case of changes the system has to be
 56 re-certified, which is a long and expensive process.

57 The company offers a Ground Station as extension
 58 to the ASVS, which only allows viewing video data or
 59 searching and exporting specific chunks of it. It
 60 doesn't have to be certified, as it is not part of the
 61 “flying equipment” and can thus be modified more
 62 easily. The idea is to transform the Ground Station into
 63 a CPS that interfaces with the CVU/DVR to offer a
 64 web-based service which archives the video data
 65 automatically and offers the access to the video data of
 66 an airline on demand via internet. Additional
 67 automatic analyses of video streams and logging data
 68 can be added in the future to provide even more
 69 services for the customer as well as system status data
 70 for maintenance (see Fig. 6.).

Fig. 6. Video Surveillance as a Service Scenario

71
 72
 73 The challenge for the company to develop an
 74 appropriate CPS is on the one hand to modify and
 75 newly assemble the Ground Station for the proposed
 76 service. Additionally, a new software will be required
 77 to handle the proposed actions for the service. As
 78 service engineering has not been the core competence
 79 of the company until now, especially support in
 80 managing the service life cycle, from ideation over
 81 Requirements Engineering and testing, is required.
 82 Customer feedback has to be collected in order to
 83 improve the service; this information can be also be fed
 84 into the ideation phase for additional services.

85 A major change for the company is the transition
 86 from selling their video surveillance solution to
 87 providing video archiving and analysis services. In
 88 order to make an innovative, but safe shift from a pure
 89 product supplier to a product-service provider, there is
 90 a need to identify if the service will be accepted by the
 91 market, possibly also in other sectors (e.g. train
 92 surveillance). Furthermore, it has to be ensured that the
 93 service business doesn't cannibalize the product
 94 business and is able to generate stable and continuous
 95 revenues. Thus, a business model innovation is
 96 required to offer the enhanced functionality to the
 97 customer.

1 **4.2. Research Issues**

2 In this section, current research issues regarding the
3 adoption of I4.0 and Smart Manufacturing are
4 presented. The identified research issues are structured
5 in three main categories: technical, methodological
6 and business case research issues. Some of the
7 discussed research issues represent aspects that could
8 be grouped within more than one of these categories.
9 In such cases, the grouping is based upon the most
10 significant factor in the eyes of the authors.

11 **4.2.1. Technical Research Issues**

12 *Standards/interfaces:* In the global economy, supply
13 networks are formed in the majority of cases by a
14 number of heterogeneous entities. Heterogeneous in
15 this case includes different dimensions like, e.g.,
16 company size, location, but also the used software
17 solutions. While some companies might choose
18 proprietary solutions available on the market, others
19 might prefer (or are forced to by, e.g., economic
20 means) self-developed or open-access solutions. When
21 companies with different systems choose to work
22 together, the interoperability is a major issue that needs
23 to be addressed to enable Smart Manufacturing. This
24 is e.g. reflected in the CPLS use case, where machines,
25 transport systems and human interface devices from
26 different vendors have to collaborate. Due to the
27 dynamic and complex nature of manufacturing, a ‘one
28 of a kind’ integration will not suffice but commonly
29 respected standards are needed to facilitate formation
30 and operation of successful Smart Manufacturing
31 supply networks.

32 *Data analytics:* Data analytics or Big Data are a core
33 component of the data based Smart Manufacturing and
34 I4.0 initiatives. Data analytics are essential to connect
35 the captured sensor (and other manufacturing/supply
36 chain related) data and the humans in the loop. The
37 increasing degree of automation of Smart
38 Manufacturing Systems with real-time data
39 availability and automated monitoring and control
40 depend on strong algorithms supporting human
41 decisions. The co-bots application case e.g.
42 emphasizes the importance of advanced and reliable
43 data analytics algorithms as it is the foundation of the
44 safe collaboration between humans and robotic
45 systems at the envisioned open shop floor.

46 *Data security issues:* I4.0 and Smart Manufacturing
47 are by definition very data focused. With CPS
48 connecting all entities and allowing real-time data
49 capturing and exchange using smart sensors and
50 wireless communication protocols. More and more
51 cloud based services provide additional functionality
52 and accessibility to manufacturing data from outside of
53 the facility. This does however come at a price: with
54 the increase in valuable data and the analytical means
55 to use them, the motivation for external parties with
56 potential criminal intent increases as well, e.g. in the
57 case of aircraft video surveillance. As the
58 manufacturing data is the core of the manufacturing
59 companies’ competitive advantage, systems need to be

60 developed to prevent unauthorized access to data. A
61 second data security issue that needs attention is the
62 access to connected machines and control systems
63 from outside the companies. Due to the high level of
64 integration and connectivity, this presents another high
65 priority target for criminal third parties, aiming at e.g.,
66 sabotage of the manufacturing processes.

67 *Data quality:* While Big Data and other data
68 analytics research streams gain significant attention,
69 the issue of data quality is similarly important [44].
70 With the increasing amount of manufacturing data
71 available, it presents a challenge to ensure the integrity
72 and quality of the captured and communicated data.
73 Low quality data may lead to results that are
74 endangering the data based optimization and
75 monitoring systems. Automated data quality
76 monitoring algorithms need to be developed and
77 evaluated in a manufacturing environment to support
78 the human users and help to improve the trust in data
79 based decisions. Another aspect of data quality is the
80 heterogeneity of manufacturing data, especially when
81 looking at the whole lifecycle of a product. The
82 annotations of the data entities are very diverse and it
83 is an increasing challenge to incorporate diverse data
84 repositories with different semantics for advanced data
85 analytics. Systems like the Semantic Mediator [45],
86 applied in the CPLS case need to be developed further
87 and included in the standards mentioned before.

88 *Sensors/actuators:* With regard to sensing systems,
89 significant progress has been achieved in recent years,
90 regarding quality of measurements, size of the systems
91 and price. However, with the increasing demand of
92 sensors and real-time control of manufacturing
93 processes like in human-robot interaction, also the
94 requirements towards sensors and the systems they are
95 embedded in increased. Reliability, energy
96 consumption and communication protocols are just a
97 few areas where more work has to be conducted for
98 adoption of Smart Manufacturing on a broad scale.

99 **4.2.1. Methodological Research Issues**

100 *Reference Models:* To enable the description of
101 complex concepts for the migration to Smart
102 Manufacturing / I4.0 and the definition of demands and
103 requirements for specific application domains,
104 reference models are needed. A Reference
105 Architecture Model has been created for Industrie 4.0
106 (RAMI 4.0) that aims to integrate the different aspects
107 required for dynamic cooperation in value networks.
108 This includes vertical networking of the means of
109 production, the workpiece and the associated data, as
110 well as horizontal networking beyond the single
111 factory towards the formation of dynamic value
112 networks.

113 In order to integrate all technical and commercial
114 aspects in one model, the perspectives of different
115 application domains had to be understood. Existing
116 approaches have been identified (e.g. IEC 62541,
117 ISO13584-42 or ProSTEP iViP), but cover only partial
118 aspects of the envisaged holistic view. The resulting

1 model contains the main aspects of Industrie 4.0 (see
2 Fig. 7.).

3
4 Source: ZVEI, Platform Industrie 4.0 [46]

5 **Fig. 7.** Reference Architecture Model Industrie 4.0

6 Hierarchy levels based on IEC 62264 are extended
7 by a ‘Product’ and a ‘Connected World’ level. The life
8 cycle of products and machines is represented
9 horizontally, distinguished between types and
10 individual instances. Finally, six layers describe the IT
11 representation of an I4.0 component in a structured
12 way. Special characteristics of RAMI 4.0 are the
13 combination of life cycle and value stream with a
14 structured approach to define I4.0 components. RAMI
15 4.0 is about to be standardized as DIN SPEC 91345.

16 *Visualization:* Visualization is grouped under
17 methodological issues but has also a strong technical
18 part. Visualization is an important vehicle to
19 communicate the complex results of data analytics to
20 the stakeholders, such as the recorded video streams
21 and operational data from the aircraft surveillance case.
22 It is challenging as the stakeholders have very different
23 foci and requirement towards the visualization and
24 granularity of the presented results. Visualization
25 offers to illustrate the different levels, from very
26 detailed, e.g., machine tool level, to an overview, e.g.,
27 supply chain, level. Research and industry need to
28 work together on driving visualization research as it is
29 a critical part of Smart Manufacturing acceptance in
30 real life.

31 *Service/app marketplaces:* It has been mentioned
32 multiple times that Smart Manufacturing is an
33 interdisciplinary field, with strong ties between
34 engineering and computer science. App/Service
35 marketplaces gained significant attention in recent
36 years as they offer flexibility, transparency and (in
37 some cases) accreditation/security features. The
38 advances in cloud computing (cloud manufacturing)
39 support this claim. Flexible app/service marketplaces
40 that offer a set of core apps and allow users or
41 independent third parties to develop customized apps
42 focusing on certain issues in the Smart Manufacturing
43 realm are desired by industry and research. User-
44 developed apps can range from granular scheduling
45 apps to advanced supply chain wide data analytics apps.
46 The aircraft surveillance system provider plans to offer
47 advanced video analysis services, some of which could
48 also be developed by third parties. There is a
49 significant overlap with research issue in

50 interfaces/standards, visualization, data analytics, data
51 security and reference models etc.

52 *Requirements Engineering:* Inadequate
53 Requirements Engineering (RE) is one of the main
54 sources for the failure of development projects and
55 culminates in exceeding budgets, missing
56 functionalities or even the abortion of the project [47].
57 Therefore, in the context of Smart Manufacturing,
58 adequate Requirements Engineering is also the key to
59 success or failure of every CPS. Ensuring
60 communication and consistency of requirements for
61 CPS is a challenge due to the variety of stakeholders
62 from different domains involved. Furthermore,
63 viewing CPS as a system of systems, the independence
64 of its elements and their evolutionary nature are
65 challenging. This leads to exceptionally distributed RE
66 activities with isolated RE approaches. In the aircraft
67 surveillance case, the new service engineering
68 department was initially organizationally separated
69 from hardware and software engineering. This
70 complexity leaves requirements fragmented among
71 many disciplines and sometimes conflicting, unstable,
72 unknowable or not fully defined. RE processes need to
73 be able to handle competing stakeholder demands and
74 dynamically respond to continually changing
75 requirements. Finally, the properties of the CPS are not
76 the sum of the properties of its elements. Rather, they
77 emerge from the cumulative interactions of the single
78 systems. Therefore, RE methods and tools have to be
79 able to manage emergent effects with predictable
80 results [48].

81 Geisberger and Broy [8] emphasize the central role
82 of Requirements Engineering for CPS development,
83 integration, maintenance and evolution. According to
84 their research agenda, main topics in this area include
85 involving users and other stakeholders from different
86 domains actively into CPS development from the
87 beginning, adaption of CPS to needs, habits and
88 competences of the users, specification of formal
89 requirements models, detailing of requirements and
90 mapping them to system elements, integration of
91 mechanical engineering models with digital models
92 from software and systems engineering for the
93 collaborative description of requirements, as well as
94 their implementation, validation, evolution and
95 communication between stakeholders from different
96 disciplines. Penzenstadler and Eckhardt [49] introduce
97 a RE content model for requirements elicitation and
98 documentation at different levels that would have to be
99 adopted by all stakeholders involved. Wiesner et al.
100 [50] propose Natural Language Processing (NLP) as a
101 way to translate non-formal requirements to formal
102 descriptions in different disciplines, thus enabling
103 automated information processing. NLP techniques
104 can assist requirements engineers when writing
105 specifications, transforming requirements in natural
106 language into discipline specific models.

1 **4.2.1. Business Case Issues**

2 *Privacy issues:* Privacy issues are strongly related to
 3 data security issues. However, in this case it was
 4 decided to separate the two areas. Whereas data
 5 security issues focus more on the technical ability to
 6 protect and preserve sensitive (manufacturing) data,
 7 privacy issues in this case describe challenges
 8 regarding the exchange of data, information and/or
 9 knowledge within the company itself and within the
 10 supply network. With the dawn of Smart
 11 Manufacturing and the connected company, detailed
 12 manufacturing data is available for advanced analytics.
 13 However, this presents a major thread for the core
 14 competencies of specialized manufacturers. By
 15 obtaining precious data, competitors are able to not
 16 only ‘reverse engineer’ the products but, even more
 17 problematic, derive the underlying knowledge and
 18 capabilities. On the other hand, within supply networks,
 19 companies may work together which are competitors
 20 in a different segment of the market. E.g. video data
 21 from aircraft surveillance belongs to the airline, is
 22 stored by the service provider and is regulated by
 23 passenger privacy, with laws differing between
 24 countries. Within the supply network, the sharing of
 25 information is beneficial for multiple reasons, e.g.,
 26 quality improvements [51]. Developing mechanisms
 27 that ensure that the data is used only for the purpose it
 28 is shared requires interdisciplinary research involving,
 29 policy, law, business, computer science and
 30 engineering experts.

31 *Investment issues:* The authors debated if this
 32 ‘(initial) investment issue’ should be included in the
 33 list as this is a rather general issue which stands true
 34 for most new technology based initiatives in
 35 manufacturing. However, in this case, the authors
 36 believe that the interdisciplinary nature and
 37 complexity of Smart Manufacturing installments
 38 present (real or imagined) barriers especially for SMEs.
 39 Implementing Smart Manufacturing frameworks in a
 40 SME, such as the CPLS system, may require a
 41 significant investment without a full estimation of the
 42 break even point from the start. The reliance on
 43 collaboration and the subsequent possibilities of
 44 process and organizational improvements are hard to
 45 measure. The authors believe that strong Testbeds as
 46 put together by the SMLC or Lighthouse projects
 47 (I4.0) are a good start to establish benchmarks and
 48 successful examples highlighting the potential of such
 49 an investment. However, there is a need for theoretical
 50 research regarding the quantification and ROI on
 51 Smart Manufacturing applications especially for SMEs
 52 including the effects of collaboration in complex and
 53 dynamic supply networks.

54 *Servitized Business Models:* In the manufacturing
 55 industry, Business Models (BM) have traditionally
 56 focused on the fabrication or assembly of more or less
 57 customized (physical) products and have generated
 58 revenue from their sales. The therefore required
 59 machines, materials and qualified personnel cause high
 60 fix costs, so supply chain organization and efficiency

61 have had a high influence on competitiveness [52].
 62 However, these traditional BMs have come under
 63 pressure with the global harmonization of
 64 technological standards and the reduction of trade
 65 barriers. Many researchers have suggested that
 66 manufacturing firms in developed economies should
 67 expand their role in the value chain by extending their
 68 products with services so they do not have to compete
 69 solely on cost [53,54]. Neely et al. [55] published a
 70 study that shows five fundamental developments: “(1)
 71 the shift from a world of products to a world including
 72 solutions, (2) outputs to outcomes, (3) transactions to
 73 relationships, (3) suppliers to network partners, and
 74 (5) elements to ecosystems.” The result are so called
 75 Product-Service Systems (PSS), a framework
 76 describing the integrated development, realization and
 77 offering of specific product-service bundles as a
 78 solution for the customer [9].

79 This is fully in line with the idea of Smart
 80 Manufacturing, where CPS provide the solution for a
 81 certain problem through the outcome of their
 82 application. Instead of one-off sales transactions, CPS
 83 build relationships with other systems and their
 84 environment. For example, access to lifecycle (usage)
 85 data may allow the manufacturers to improve their
 86 processes and offer additional services around their
 87 core product, as in the case of aircraft video
 88 surveillance. As a result, suppliers, customers and
 89 other partners become part of a networked ecosystem
 90 around the CPS. Gorldt et al. [56] have coined the term
 91 “Cyber-physical Product-Service System” (CPSS) for
 92 the integration of the PSS concept and Smart
 93 Manufacturing. A manufacturing enterprise however
 94 that changes from the fabrication of products to
 95 offering CPSS solutions and transforms its supplier
 96 base into an ecosystem of network partners will have
 97 to analyze and adapt various elements of its BM to stay
 98 profitable and competitive. According to Osterwalder
 99 and Pigneur [57], these elements comprise not only the
 100 new value proposition, but also different customer
 101 segments and relationships, distribution channels, key
 102 resources, activities and relationship, as well as a
 103 changed cost structure and revenue streams. This
 104 creates several challenges for the company (see Fig. 8.).

Fig. 8. Business Model Innovation

105
 106
 107 From an internal viewpoint on how to develop and
 108 realize the CPSS. How are risks and opportunities
 109 distributed among the network partners? What is the
 110 innovation effort compared to amortization time? But
 111 as well from an external viewpoint on the CPSS offer.
 112 What is the added value for the customer and the value
 113 of data? Who is paying for which results?

1 The task for manufacturing enterprises is to
 2 integrate the new and unknown value proposition of a
 3 CPSS and the associated collaborative arrangements
 4 into their BM without experience in this field. Building
 5 networks with unconventional business partners is
 6 difficult and can bring incalculable risks. Innovative
 7 technologies have to be utilized for service provision
 8 and to develop closer relationships to the customer.
 9 New stakeholders in the ecosystem affect the cost
 10 structure and require new kinds of revenue models,
 11 which are currently not elaborated in manufacturing
 12 industries. Wiesner et al. [58] have developed an
 13 approach, based on methods like the “Blue Ocean
 14 Strategy” [59] and the BM Canvas [57], which
 15 supports manufacturing enterprises in this transition.

16 5. Conclusions

17 In this paper, the fourth industrial revolution, called
 18 ‘Industrie 4.0’ (Germany/EU) and Smart
 19 Manufacturing (USA) has been in the focus. The
 20 momentum and traction both initiatives (and similar
 21 ones in several other countries) gained in recent years
 22 highlights the rapid, paradigm shifting change the
 23 manufacturing industry and manufacturing research
 24 are undergoing today. I4.0 and Smart Manufacturing
 25 describe the transition towards a heavily data focused,
 26 supply network wide integration of information and
 27 communication technology and increased automation,
 28 while keeping the human in the loop. The goals are
 29 manifold and diverse, with energy saving,
 30 sustainability (social, economic and environmental),
 31 agility/resilience, as well as quality and efficiency
 32 improvements being in the center.

33 Several application scenarios were presented that
 34 have highlighted the wide scope of Smart
 35 Manufacturing. One application case focused on a
 36 cyber-physical logistics system for intralogistics that
 37 could reduce Kanban cycles and distances. The second
 38 one highlighted human robot interaction on the shop
 39 floor and how I4.0 can ensure the safety of the human
 40 worker and co-bot working together in close proximity.
 41 The third use case gave insights in the application of
 42 video streams and operational data from an aircraft
 43 cabin surveillance system to offer new and enhanced
 44 archiving and analysis services through an innovative
 45 business model. The three use cases from different
 46 domains present a small selection of the diverse
 47 applications and challenges I4.0 and Smart
 48 Manufacturing have to deal with on the one hand, and
 49 what huge potential lies in these new initiatives.

50 After the application cases were presented, current
 51 and future research issues were derived and illustrated.
 52 Three main categories, technical, methodological and
 53 business case challenges were chosen to structure the
 54 different research issues. It has to be noted, that while
 55 the list of research issues is long already, the issues
 56 identified and discussed are rather high level and the
 57 list does not claim to be comprehensive. The research
 58 issues selected for presentation in this paper were

59 mainly based on the three use cases. As Smart
 60 Manufacturing and I4.0 are such overarching,
 61 paradigm shifting initiatives, there are many more
 62 research issues relevant today and most likely even
 63 more tomorrow (in the future). The more I4.0 and
 64 Smart Manufacturing are accepted and adopted by
 65 industry and academia, the more different fields and
 66 research areas discover the potential of their work
 67 within the greater system, the more traction Smart
 68 manufacturing and I4.0 will get and the more research
 69 issues will surface.

70 While there are already successful testbeds available,
 71 I4.0 and Smart Manufacturing are still in their early
 72 stages. Given the attention and available grants from
 73 funding agencies and the severe interest from industry
 74 (both large corporations and SMEs), it can be expected
 75 that the near future will present rapid developments in
 76 this area. Due to its interdisciplinary nature, advances
 77 in basic research fields may find their way to industrial
 78 application more rapidly than it was the case in past
 79 years. This may be a chance for researchers who have
 80 not had much interaction with applied research in their
 81 field to collaborate with researchers of supplementing
 82 fields and industry to see their work being used in real
 83 life applications.

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